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ABSTRACTS

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**Precision Autism Spectrum Disorder Prediction through Machine Learning:
A Comprehensive Framework for Enhanced Early Detection and
Personalized Intervention**

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Abstract: Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), a neurodevelopmental condition, poses challenges in social interaction, communication, and repetitive behaviors, exhibiting a spectrum of symptoms with varying severity. Early detection is crucial for timely intervention, but conventional methods are often delayed and subjective. Our project introduces a novel approach, employing advanced machine learning to predict ASD early and enable personalized interventions. Leveraging diverse datasets, including behavioral observations, neuroimaging, and genetic markers, our computational framework focuses on behavioral data to develop a robust predictive model. The classification algorithm achieves high accuracy, outperforming existing methods with up to 87% accuracy. The model's significance is underscored by the limitations of current diagnostic methods, the potential for early intervention, and the global rise in ASD prevalence. Beyond accurate prediction, our framework facilitates personalized interventions based on individual characteristics and response patterns, marking a paradigm shift toward precision medicine in neurodevelopmental disorders. The application provides real-time evaluation and user-friendly questions for both parents and children. Rigorous validation on diverse datasets confirms the model's efficacy, emphasizing improved sensitivity and specificity. In conclusion, our innovative project revolutionizes ASD prediction and intervention through machine learning. By integrating diverse datasets and prioritizing individualized strategies, we contribute to advancing diagnostic and therapeutic approaches for ASD. Anticipating a substantial impact, our work aims to enhance outcomes and deepen the understanding of the complex factors influencing ASD.

Keywords: Autism spectrum disorder, machine learning, personalized intervention, neuroimaging, genetic markers, predictive modeling, precision medicine.

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